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“BRAND EQUITY OF INDIAN AUTOMOBILE SECTOR” (WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO MYSURU CITY ONLY)

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ABSTRACT

Brands are now seen as "cultural accessories and personal beliefs," and they are becoming a more significant part of both the economy and culture. The process of developing a brand is a value-adding strategy that promotes the image of the good, the firm, and the nation as a whole. The study's goal is to outline the brand equity measurement technique that may be used in the auto sector. The study's findings indicate that both consumer preferences and the state of the industry as a whole have changed and improved over the past several years. To achieve a consistent perception of the company and for customers to see the value, the brand equity components must act consistently.

Keywords: Brand, Brand loyalty, Brand awareness, Perceived quality, Brand association and Brand asset. Indian car industry.

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I. INTRODUCTION

A brand is a name or trademark connected with a product or producer. Brands have become increasingly important components of culture and the economy, now being described as "cultural accessories and personal philosophies". Brands are valued for their equity; they add value. Everyone in the marketing profession agrees that brands can add substantial value. It is a fact that sometimes that brand becomes a burden. It is established that brands can be value enhancers and also decrease profit. The brand building process is a value-adding technique that projects the image of the product, the company, and the country at large. A brand strategy aids businesses in achieving their targeted performance. The area of brand equity has received significant research attention in recent years. The study of brand equity is becoming increasingly popular as some marketing researchers have concluded that brands are one of the most valuable assets that companies possess. As a result, current marketing research attempts to conceptualize, measure, and manage brand equity in a way that drives brand market performance and helps firms in strategic decision-making. This paper gives an empirical outcome of the determinants of brand equity with special reference to the Indian car industry. (Natarajan, 2011)

"Brand equity is a set of brand assets and liabilities linked to a brand; its name and symbol add to or subtract from the value provided by a product or service to a firm and/or to the firm's customers" (David, 1991)

"Brand equity is defined in terms of marketing effects uniquely attributable to brands. For example, when certain outcomes result from the marketing of a product or service because of its brand name, that would not occur if the same product or service did not have the name" (Keller, 1993)

Brand equity refers to the marketing effects or outcomes that accrue to a product with its brand name compared with those that would accrue if the same product did not have the brand name. It is to observe that at the root of these marketing effects is consumers' knowledge. In other words, consumers' knowledge about a brand makes manufacturers or advertisers respond differently or adopt appropriately adept measures for the marketing of the brand (Natarajan, 2011).

1.2 AIM OF THE STUDY

The aim of this study is to find out has a particular brand created any impact in the young customer's mind, the image of being the go to brand of car by providing all the features that would satisfy their needs.

1.3 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

- The study includes a mixed population of students, officials, service man, professionals.
- This study captured the brand equity of Mysuru customers of different brands.
- The study is directed towards studying the customer insights of buying or using a particular brand of car.

1.4 OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- To develop a customer based brand equity.
- To study how the brand equity of a brand is affected by brand awareness, brand loyalty, brand association.

1.5 PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of the study is to understand does the customers’ value on a brand increase the brand equity of a brand.

1.6 LIMATIONS OF THE STUDY

- The sample size is limited to 200 respondents only.
- The study was carried out in Mysuru region only.

1.7 STATISTICAL TOOLS USED

To analyse the data collected the statistical tools which were used are:

- Reliability test
- Correlation
- Regression

1.8 FINDINGS

The study shows that brand loyalty, brand association, perceived quality, brand asset does play an important role in determining the brand equity of a particular brand. The different brand of cars have worked on the brand equity because in the study we could clearly see that the preferences of the customers have changed a lot when compared to what it was about five to ten years age where only select few brand used to dominate the entire Indian automobile sector, but now due to increased competition with the entry of foreign brands the market is divided where every brand which entered Indian market has its own identity and has its own set of brand loyal customers.

1.9 MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS

As a brand manager for a particular brand he/she should ensure that their brand of car standouts in the market by providing:

- Good experience during the buying process to the customer.
- The manager shouldn’t just see a customer meeting sales target but they should see the customer in a long term perspective, this could be achieved by giving the customer the best possible answers to their questions, being the one-point access throughout the buying process and also post purchase too.
- Recommend different brand car if the type of car a customer is looking for isn’t available in your brand, even though they wouldn’t be your customer but will remember you for a long time and at some point in future would defiantly become a customer of your brand.
- As a brand manager he/she should take reviews of the product from the customers and convey the most commonly requested feature or most commonly pointed out pain points to the product, to the product design team so that they could resolve it when they are designing the updated version of the same product before the launch of the product.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.1 INTRODUCTION

Generally, brand equity is examined from two different perspectives: financial and customer-based. In this report, the first perspective of brand equity, that is, its financial aspect, is not discussed. The report measures brand equity based on customer responses to a few selected questions.

2.2 REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The study of brand equity is becoming increasingly popular as some researchers have concluded that brands are one of the most valuable assets that a company has to offer. (Lee, 2011). High brand equity levels are known to lead to higher consumer preferences and purchase intentions (Cobb-Walgren, 1995). Besides, high brand equity brings an opportunity for successful extensions, resilience against competitors' promotional pressures, and the creation of barriers to competitive entry (Farquhar P. , 1993).

Initially, brand equity was conceptualised as consisting of consumers' brand associations that included brand awareness, knowledge, and image (Keller, 1993). As stated earlier, brand equity is regarded as consisting of two components: brand strength and brand value (Srivastava and Shocker, 1991). Our interest is in brand strength, which is defined by the brand associations held by the brand's customers. Some researchers view brand equity as the perceived brand quality of both the brand's tangible and intangible components (Kamakura and Russell, 1991). According to (Cathy J. Cobb-Walgren, 1995), the issue of brand equity has emerged as one of the most critical areas for marketing management in the 1990s. This study explores some of the consequences of brand equity. In particular, it examines the effect of brand equity on consumer preferences and purchase intentions. For comparative purposes, two sets of brands were tested: one from a service category characterised by fairly high financial and functional risk (hotels); and another from a generally lower-risk product category (household cleansers). Each set includes two brands that are objectively similar (based on Consumer Reports ratings), but they have invested in markedly different levels of advertising spending over the past decade. Across both categories, the brand with the higher advertising budget yielded substantially higher levels of brand equity. In turn, the brand with higher equity in each category generated significantly greater preferences and purchase intentions.

According to (Chang, 2009), the antecedents of brand equity are considered to be brand attitude and brand image, and the consequences of brand equity are considered to be brand preference and purchase intentions. This study concentrates on service brands, selecting 18 from 3 service categories. A structural equation model is presented. Not only does it show a good fit with the research constructs but also the relationships between brand image and brand equity as well as brand attitude and brand equity. The impact of brand equity on customer preference and purchase intentions is confirmed as well, which tends to validate the proposed research framework.

(Raju, 2009), The outcome of brand positioning is brand perception, which can be gathered from multiple routes, including customer experiences, marketing communication efforts, and word of mouth. Perception of the brand is critical, as is evident from the huge amount of money being spent by organisations on brand development and measurement. Still, very little is known about the relationship between brand perception and customer behaviour, including customer loyalty. This study has been conducted empirically by testing two hypotheses about the relationship between brand perception and brand loyalty. The first part of the research shows very little evidence that any one brand attribute is more relevant or related to brand loyalty than other brand attributes. The second part observes that a higher number of attribute associations with a brand leads to higher brand loyalty. It also emphasises that brand uniqueness is critical in getting the customer's attention. However, the source to create that uniqueness is critical in getting the customer's attention. In addition to the above, the paper discusses different short and long-term strategies for brand development.

Any discussion on Brand Equity has to first begin by understanding what a brand is. The American Marketing Association defines brand as —a name, term, sign, symbol, or design, or a combination of them intended to identify the goods and services of one seller or group of sellers to differentiate them from those of competition (Shariq, 2018). Sokolowski (1989) –

—at its root a brand is a mark of distinction that differentiates one thing from another: at one level, it is a material act; on the other, a philosophic process. A product is something that offers a functional benefit (e.g., a toothpaste, a life insurance policy, or a car). A brand is a name, symbol, design, or mark that enhances the value of a product beyond its functional purpose (Farquhar P. H., 1989). (David, 1991) qualifies this definition by saying that —a brand thus signals to the customer the source of the product, and protects both the customer and the producer from competitors who would attempt to provide products that appear to be identical.

2.3 GAP ANALYSIS

The review of literature reveals that many of the brand equity studies which are done are based on service sector and Fast Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) products. There are some studies which are done on brand equity of automobile sector but there are either studied on a single brand or comparison of two or three brands of cars, also if the study is done on whole automobile sector of India it is out dated and the industry has changed dramatically with the entry of new foreign brands into the market and the changed strategies of the Indian firms to overcome the challenges faced by the foreign brands. The competition in the Indian market has increases and these changes are also due to the regulatory changes made by the Indian government in terms of minimum safety requirements and other norms which were considered as luxury then, now all are the basic feature which is a must have, to be able to sell cars in India. So there is a need for new updated study which will cover all the new changes in the industry and study the increased competition. This study tries to cover most of the new changes which are included in the regulatory norms.

RESEARCH DESIGN

3.1 INTRODUCTION

Research design is a broad plan that states objectives of research project and provides the guidelines what is to be done to realize those objectives. It is, in other words, a master plan for executing a research project. But in the relation to the subject concern, it is a pattern or an outline of research projects workings.

3.2 OBJECTIVE

- To develop a customer based brand equity.
- To study how the brand equity of a brand is affected by brand awareness, brand loyalty, brand association.

3.3 SAMPLING METHOD

The sample size is computed using a formula shown below. Substitution of value of p as 0.8, q as 0.2, e as 0.05, and z as 1.96 is made. P is the probability of occurrence and q is probability of non-occurrence. E is standard error and z is confidence level. The sample size 132 thought to be adequate one. As there would be errors, 100 samples were considered.

For the calculation of sample size, the following formula has been used.

$$n = z^2(pq)/e^2$$

Where, P is the probability of occurrence, q is probability of non-occurrence. E is standard error and z is confidence level.

The methodology was based on the development of a self-administered questionnaire using a computed sample size. The study is descriptive in nature. The study is based on primary data collected through survey research. Structured questionnaire is used as the research instrument

which is administered through personal interview and interview through telephone calls to 132 respondents from the different regions of Mysuru.

3.4 DATA COLLECTION

Data were collected through survey using a structured questionnaire having 24 questions covering all the factors along with the demographics. Totally 132 samples were collected. Respondents were users of different brands of cars listed in the survey. Sample for the study consisted of all the age group. Data were collected from targeted population of Mysuru.

Questionnaires were handed over to them with a request for filling at the spot. The questionnaire had the following dimensions.

- Demographics such as age, qualification, etc.
- Questions on each of the factor asking about what the customers wanted.

3.5 PRIMARY DATA

The questionnaire was presented to the audience and response were collected. The variable that use in forming the questions were Brand loyalty, Brand awareness, Perceived quality, Brand association, and Brand asset.

3.6 QUESTIONNAIRE DESIGN

The independent variables are Brand loyalty, Brand awareness, Perceived quality, Brand association, and Brand asset. Each independent variable has three questions each. The dependent variable has four questions. Demographics that were considered are age group, educational qualification and their occupation.

All the variables were measured with a 5 point Liker scale, where 1 being Strongly disagree, 2 being Disagree, 3 being Neutral, 4 bring Agree and 5 being Strongly agree.

3.7 CONCEPTUAL MODEL

3.8 HYPOTHESIS

- Brand Loyalty:
 - H0: Brand loyalty significantly influences brand equity.
 - H1: Brand loyalty doesn't influence brand equity.
- Brand awareness:
 - H0: Brand awareness significantly influences brand equity.
 - H1: Brand awareness doesn't influence brand equity.
- Brand asset:
 - H0: Brand asset significantly influences brand equity.
 - H1: Brand asset doesn't influence brand equity.

- Brand association:
 - H0: Brand association significantly influences brand equity.
 - H1: Brand association doesn't influence brand association.

3.9 VARIABLES DESCRIPTION

Brand loyalty:

Brand loyalty is perception-based (image and experience). Brand-loyal customers believe that a certain brand represents both higher quality and better service than any competitor—and the price does not matter. Brand-loyal customers might make fewer total purchases, but the profit margins on their purchases are larger. Once established, brand loyalty is fairly easy to retain—assuming, of course, that product quality and service level remain high. Brand loyalty is also less expensive to retain than customer loyalty, which requires constantly offering low prices and regular discounts to maintain best-deal-on-the-market status (Kopp, Investopedia , 2022).

Brand loyalty is the loyalty or faithfulness which a customer develops for a brand. Brand loyalty is developed in the mind of a consumer after find the product or service useful. Brand loyalty is an important aspect of marketing as it helps companies build a strong brand and get the customers again. Brand loyalty is not simply rebuying the products but creating a positive brand image in the consumer's mind, who becomes a positive brand advocate (MBA Skool, 2020).

Brand awareness:

Brand awareness is a marketing term that describes the degree of consumer recognition of a product by its name. Creating brand awareness is a key step in promoting a new product or reviving an older brand. Ideally, awareness of the brand may include the qualities that distinguish the product from its competition (Kopp, Investopedia , 2022).

Brand awareness is the likelihood as to how aware a customer is about a brand, product or service. Brand awareness is how much a customer or prospect recalls or recollects about a particular company & its goods. Brand awareness is one of the key dimensions of brand equity & it includes a customer's ability to remember the product, logo, tagline, name etc. (MBA Skool, 2020).

Perceived quality:

Perceived quality can be defined as the customer's opinion about the overall quality or image of the product or service or the brand itself with respect to its purpose of use as against its alternatives. Perceived quality might not be linked to the actual product but is more skewed towards the brand image, customer experience with the brand and its other products, peer opinions, etc. Thus perceived quality differs from objective quality, product-based quality and manufacturing quality (MBA Skool team, 2019).

Perceived quality is a reason for customer to buy and differentiate a brand from other brands. According to (David, 1991) perceived quality is an important dimension of customer based brand equity. However, it refers to the subjective evaluation of the product by the consumer. Perceived quality is one core component of brand equity that can be used to measure brand equity. It is also a dimension of brand value. Perceived quality is a customer feeling toward brand. The real success of a service provider is dependent on the perceived quality of the services provided to its customers. Literature suggest there exist a relationship among perceived quality, customer satisfaction, and firm profitability (Zeithaml V. , 1988)(Kotler, 2000).

Brand association:

A brand association is a mental connection a customer makes between your brand and a concept, image, emotion, experience, person, interest, or activity. This association can be immediately positive or negative and it heavily influences purchase decisions. Brands want to

create positive associations and ideally, brand associations are simple, positive, and immediate (Holmes, 2021).

Brand association forms the basis of consumer purchase decision. Brand association reflects consumer's memory about brand. The level of brand association can be increased by having frequent communication with the customers (David, 1991). Brand association can help customer retrieve information related to brand, differentiate the brand, develop a reason to purchase the brand, develop a favourable, positive attitude towards the brand, and develop basis for brand extension.

Brand asset:

Brand assets are elements, such as a colour scheme, jingle or font that help identify a specific brand. These elements become brand assets only when customers associate them with a brand. If an element leads the audience to a different but similar brand, that element is not an asset (Schmidt, 2020).

3.10 STATISTICAL TOOLS USED

The statistical tools which were used to understand the collected data were reliability analysis, correlation and regression.

Cronbach's alpha (reliability test) is a measure of internal consistency, that is, how closely related a set of items are as a group. It is considered to be a measure of scale reliability. A "high" value for alpha does not imply that the measure is unidimensional. If, in addition to measuring internal consistency, you wish to provide evidence that the scale in question is unidimensional, additional analyses can be performed. Exploratory factor analysis is one method of checking dimensionality. Technically speaking, Cronbach's alpha is not a statistical test – it is a coefficient of reliability (or consistency) (UCLA, 2021).

Correlation is a statistical term describing the degree to which two variables move in coordination with one another. If the two variables move in the same direction, then those variables are said to have a positive correlation. If they move in opposite directions, then they have a negative correlation (Hayes, 2022).

Regression analysis is a set of statistical methods used for the estimation of relationships between a dependent variable and one or more [independent variables](#). It can be utilized to assess the strength of the relationship between variables and for modelling the future relationship between them (CFI team , 2022).

DATA ANALYSIS

Age group	Number of respondents
18-25	94
26-33	23
34-41	12
42 & above	3

Table 4.1

Most of the respondents are in the age group of 18-25 (with 71.2%, that is 94 of the respondents) and the age group 26-33 falls second in the survey with 23 respondents falling under this age group, the age group 34-41 age group is third with 9.1% (that is 12 respondents falling under this age group) of the overall survey respondent. About 2.3% that is (3 number of respondents) fall under the age group of 42 & above.

Educational Qualification	Number of respondents
10 th	2
PUC	1
Under graduate	69
Post graduate	57
PhD	3

Table 4.2

Table 4.2 gives information about the educational background of the respondents who took the survey. About 52.3% (that is 69 members of the respondents) of the respondent have completed their graduation, and about 43.2% (that is 57 members of the respondents) of the respondent have completed their post-graduation, the remaining 4.5% of the respondents have completed their 10th, PUC, and PhD.

Occupation	Number of respondents
Students	66
Self employed	14
Corporate employee	39
Government employee	3
Service sector employee	10

Table 4.3

The table 4.3 shows that nearly have of the respondents are student (i.e.50% of the respondents), 29.5% of the respondents are corporate employees, 10.6% of the respondents are self-employed, 7.6% of the respondents are into service sector meaning they are into professions like teaching, consulting, etc. and the last 2.3% of the respondent are employed in the government sector.

KMO

KMO and Bartlett's Test for Independent Variables		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.904
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	783.747
	df	78
	Sig.	.000

KMO test measures sampling adequacy for each variable calculated as 0.904 as the above table. The sampling size to be adequate the KMO value should be greater than 0.5 cent C.A., & Kaiser H.F. (1997). Values ranging from 0.6 to 0.7 say that the adequacy is meritorious. Hence the sampling adequacy for items of Independent variable is meritorious. Stating it is acceptable

Component	Total Variance Explained								
	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	6.125	47.114	47.114	6.125	47.114	47.114	3.652	28.089	28.089
2	1.162	8.937	56.050	1.162	8.937	56.050	2.557	19.669	47.758
3	.958	7.370	63.420	.958	7.370	63.420	1.472	11.320	59.078
4	.797	6.133	69.553	.797	6.133	69.553	1.362	10.475	69.553
5	.663	5.098	74.651						
6	.638	4.910	79.561						
7	.578	4.444	84.005						
8	.489	3.758	87.763						
9	.396	3.047	90.810						
10	.360	2.769	93.579						
11	.310	2.388	95.967						
12	.270	2.074	98.041						
13	.255	1.959	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

The first part of the above table shows the variance of all 13 components of the % independent variable forming the cumulating up to 100. Which depicts the all 13 items play a significance role in their respective percentage. The later part of the table shows after the extraction of fixed components under 4 extraction formed 4 factor where 47.114% of 1st factor, 56.050% of 2nd factor, 63.420% of 3rd factor, 69.553% of the 4th factor depicting that the 4 factor is replicating or signifying only by 69.553%. Which also says that the left percentage is filled by the unnamed factors. (KIM &MULLER (1978).

Rotated Component Matrix ^a				
	Component			
	1	2	3	4
Q14	.762			
Q13	.720			
Q5	.707			
Q15	.671			
Q11	.651			
Q12	.602			
Q1		.812		
Q2		.774		
Q8		.636		
Q4			.803	
Q10			.625	
Q6				.840
Q9				.531
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization. ^a				
a. Rotation converged in 9 iterations.				

KMO for Dependent variable

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.770
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	175.983
	df	6
	Sig.	.000

KMO test measures sampling adequacy for each variable calculated as 0.770 as the above table. The sampling size to be adequate the KMO value should be greater than 0.5 cent C.A., &Kaiser H.F. (1997). Values ranging from 0.6 to 0.7 say that the adequacy is meritorious. Hence the sampling adequacy for items of Independent variable is meritorious. Stating it is acceptable.

Total Variance Explained						
Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.574	64.340	64.340	2.574	64.340	64.340
2	.581	14.516	78.856			
3	.513	12.822	91.677			
4	.333	8.323	100.000			
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.						

The first part of the above table shows the variance of all 4 items of the 1-dependent variable forming the cumulating up to 100. Which depicts that the all 4 items play a significance role in their respective percentages. The later part of the table shows after the extraction of 1 fixed item 64.340% of 1st factor depicting that the 1 factors are replicating or signifying only by 64.340%. Which also says that the left percentage is filled by the unnamed factors (Kim & Muller (1978))

Reliability test:

CONSTRUCTS	Alpha
Brand Loyalty	.815
Brand Awareness	.581
Perceived Quality	.787
Brand Association	.705
Brand Asset	.743

Brand loyalty has Cronbach’s alpha result of .815 which means that questions in the survey were better. Brand awareness has Cronbach’s alpha result of .581 means that the questions in the survey were inappropriate. Perceived quality has Cronbach’s alpha result of .787 which means that the questions in the survey were better. Brand association has Cronbach’s alpha result of .705 which means the questions in the survey were better and Brand asset has Cronbach’s alpha result of .743 which means the questions in the survey were better.

Correlations						
		Q16	Q17	Q18	Q19	REGR factor score 1 for analysis 1
Q16	Pearson Correlation	1	.595**	.434**	.512**	.792**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	132	132	132	132	132
Q17	Pearson Correlation	.595**	1	.613**	.511**	.856**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	132	132	132	132	132
Q18	Pearson Correlation	.434**	.613**	1	.475**	.785**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	132	132	132	132	132
Q19	Pearson Correlation	.512**	.511**	.475**	1	.773**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	132	132	132	132	132
REGR factor score 1 for analysis 1	Pearson Correlation	.792**	.856**	.785**	.773**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	132	132	132	132	132

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Question number 16 represents the question based on brand awareness, brand awareness is significantly positively related to REGR factor.

Question number 17 represents the question based on brand loyalty, so brand loyalty is positively strongly related to REGR factor.

Question number 18 represents brand association, brand association is significantly positively related to REGR factor.

Question number 19 represents the question based on brand asset, brand asset is significantly positively related to REGR factor.

Regression

ANOVA:

A method for assessing the contribution of an independent variable or controllable factor to the observed variation in an experimentally observed dependent variable to determine whether any of the differences between the means are statistically significant, compare the p-value to your significance level to assess the null hypothesis. The null hypothesis states that the population means are all equal. Usually, a significance level (denoted as α or alpha) of 0.05 works well. (Ronald Fisher 1921)

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.769 ^a	.591	.578	.64961206
a. Predictors: (Constant), iv4, iv3, iv2, iv1				

Table 4.4

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	77.407	4	19.352	45.857	.000 ^b
	Residual	53.593	127	.422		
	Total	131.000	131			
a. Dependent Variable: dv1						
b. Predictors: (Constant), iv4, iv3, iv2, iv1						

Table 4.5

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.608E-16	.057		.000	1.000
	iv1	.545	.057	.545	9.609	.000
	iv2	.483	.057	.483	8.505	.000
	iv3	.087	.057	.087	1.541	.126
	iv4	.230	.057	.230	4.048	.000
a. Dependent Variable: dv1						

Table 4.6

Hypothesis:

Brand awareness:

- H0: Brand awareness significantly influences brand equity.
- H1: Brand awareness doesn't influence brand equity.

Sig. value <= alpha

0.00 <= 0.05

Therefore, null hypothesis is accepted.

Brand awareness significantly influences brand equity.

Brand loyalty:

- H0: Brand loyalty significantly influences brand equity.
- H1: Brand loyalty doesn't influence brand equity.

Sig. value <= alpha

0.00 < 0.05

Therefore, null hypothesis is accepted.

Brand loyalty significantly influences brand equity.

Brand association:

- H0: Brand association significantly influences brand equity.
- H1: Brand association doesn't influence brand equity.

Sig. value <= alpha

.126 > 0.05

Therefore, null hypothesis is rejected.

Brand association doesn't influence brand equity.

Brand asset:

- H0: Brand asset significantly influences brand equity.
- H1: Brand asset doesn't influence brand equity.

Sig. value \leq alpha

.00 < 0.05

Therefore, null hypothesis is accepted.

Brand asset significantly influences brand equity.

Descriptive Statistics										
	N	Range	Mean		Std. Deviation	Variance	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
Q1	132	4.00	4.4697	.07006	.80494	.648	-1.862	.211	4.289	.419
Q2	132	3.00	4.3712	.06836	.78541	.617	-1.244	.211	1.238	.419
Q3	132	4.00	3.9773	.08768	1.00735	1.015	-.773	.211	-.064	.419
Q4	132	4.00	3.9773	.09825	1.12884	1.274	-.860	.211	-.314	.419
Q5	132	3.00	4.3561	.07225	.83009	.689	-1.076	.211	.250	.419
Q6	132	4.00	3.3106	.12409	1.42568	2.033	-.211	.211	-1.248	.419
Q7	132	4.00	4.3409	.07120	.81802	.669	-1.216	.211	1.449	.419
Q8	132	4.00	4.2879	.07014	.80580	.649	-1.372	.211	2.909	.419
Q9	132	4.00	4.1439	.07985	.91745	.842	-.954	.211	.697	.419
Q10	132	4.00	3.9167	.09622	1.10545	1.222	-.728	.211	-.416	.419
Q11	132	4.00	4.1439	.07461	.85723	.735	-.799	.211	.369	.419
Q12	132	4.00	4.1364	.07663	.88043	.775	-.884	.211	.482	.419
Q13	132	4.00	4.4167	.07297	.83841	.703	-1.468	.211	1.931	.419
Q14	132	3.00	4.4394	.06108	.70177	.492	-1.127	.211	.971	.419
Q15	132	4.00	4.2803	.08557	.98317	.967	-1.520	.211	2.143	.419
Q16	132	4.00	4.2955	.06948	.79827	.637	-1.134	.211	1.539	.419
Q17	132	3.00	4.3939	.06520	.74912	.561	-1.124	.211	.848	.419
Q18	132	3.00	4.3030	.07129	.81904	.671	-.868	.211	-.209	.419
Q19	132	4.00	4.3106	.07615	.87486	.765	-1.278	.211	1.335	.419
Valid N (listwise)	132									

Choice of brand car	Number of respondents
Honda	12
Hyundai	20
Kia Motors	11
Maruti Suzuki	24
Renault	6
Tata motors	27
Toyota	15
Volkswagen	17

Table 4.7

Table 4.4 shows that the brand preferences by the respondents are very different, few years back only two or three brands dominated the choice of the people, the respondents for this study were divided where 20.5% of the respondents choice is Tata motors, 18.2% of the respondents choice is Maruti Suzuki, 15.2% of the respondents choice is Hyundai, 12.9% of the respondents choice is Volkswagen, 11.4% of the respondents choice is Toyota, 9.1% of the respondents choice is Honda, 8.3% of the respondents choice is Kia motors and only very few people chose Renault brand.

FINDINGS, SUGGESTIONS & CONCLUSION

Findings:

The study shows that brand loyalty, brand association, perceived quality, brand asset does play an important role in determining the brand equity of a particular brand. The different brand of cars have worked on the brand equity because in the study we could clearly see that the preferences of the customers have changed a lot when compared to what it was about five to ten years ago where only select few brand used to dominate the entire Indian automobile sector, but now due to increased competition with the entry of foreign brands the market is divided where every brand which entered Indian market has its own identity and has its own set of brand loyal customers.

Suggestions:

As a brand manager for a particular brand he/she should ensure that their brand of car stand outs in the market by providing:

- Good experience during the buying process to the customer.
- The manager shouldn't just see a customer meeting sales target but they should see the customer in a long term perspective, this could be achieved by giving the customer the best possible answers to their questions, being the one-point access throughout the buying process and also post purchase too.
- Recommend different brand car if the type of car a customer is looking for isn't available in your brand, even though they wouldn't be your customer but will remember you for a long time and at some point in future would defiantly become a customer of your brand.
- As a brand manager he/she should take reviews of the product from the customers and convey the most commonly requested feature or most commonly pointed out pain points to the product, to the product design team so that they could resolve it when they are designing the updated version of the same product before the launch of the product.

Scope for further studies:

- The number of respondents are less and is confined to only Mysuru city, this does not give the whole picture of brand equity of the brand.
- When a larger population is taken into consideration we would get a clear picture of brand equity.
- Most of the respondents are students whose parents own certain brands of car, so their answers are based on that user experience.
- The selection of the population should be as such that every one of the society should be included to get the right status of the brand equity.

CONCLUSION:

The study gives some clear picture that still some people prefer cars popular brands like Hyundai and Maruti Suzuki but they don't enjoy the market share that they had about a decade

ago, this is all thanks to the increased competition from both local brands like the Tata’s and Mahindra’s and also the entry of new foreign players like Kia motors, MG, etc. As the purchasing power of the people has increased the choices of people are not limited, now it’s the consumers market go are those days where the vendors used to control the market. This study also showed that people want the brand to be more engaging with their customer’s, during some of the personal interview session with the respondents I could see that people who had the best experience with a particular brand of cars, the entire conversation was revolving only around that brand and the respondents were spreading positive word of word about the brand. The other point which the study pointed out is that the brand image of Tata motors has improved over the period of time, this can be seen in the choice of brand question in the questioner, where 27 respondent’s choice was Tata motors out of 132 respondents. This shows that the company have really worked on their brand image to raise their overall brand equity, the latest line up of cars from the Tata motors has grabbed a lot of attention of the consumers and the level of certification it received like “the safest hatch back car with global NCAP rating of five stars” has really up their ante in the Indian automobile sector.

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